

The Nexus between Corporate Social Responsibility and Political Stability: A Moderated Regression Analysis in Rivers State, Nigeria

Bello Adams (PhD)¹ Donatus Onyenenu²

¹Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria

²Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria

Corresponding Author's Email: bello.adams@unidel.edu.ng

Abstract: Numerous multinational companies, such as the Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) in Rivers State, Nigeria, invest heavily in CSR programmes to support their host communities. Nonetheless challenges such as political instability, communal strife, and mistrust between companies and communities still in place. This may imply that a number of CSR initiatives are not addressing the true needs of the people. The research investigates the impact of four CSR domains, namely, corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability practices, ethical operations, and community participation, on community welfare and organizational success. It further investigated the effect of political instability on these relationships. The research was grounded in the Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984) and adopted a descriptive survey design. Questionnaires were administered to 250 respondents who comprised oil and gas company workers, members of host communities, and local government officials in Rivers State. The obtained data were analyzed using Pearson correlation and moderated multiple regression analysis through SPSS Version 27. The results showed a positive and significant influence of all four CSR activities on community impact and organizational performance with coefficients ranging from $\beta = .22$ to $\beta = .32$ ($p \leq .05$). Ethical practices ($\beta = .32$) had the largest effect followed by community participation ($\beta = .27$). Furthermore, the findings demonstrated that political instability significantly weakened the positive relations between CSR initiatives and community and corporate results ($\Delta R^2 = .048$; $p < .05$). The effect was strongest for ethical practices and community engagement. The study concludes that CSR Programmes can improve community welfare and organizational performance may be more successful in stable political environments without conflict. The study further urges multinational corporations to give more attention to community participation in decision making, to strengthen ethical accountability, to adequately monitor environmental commitments, and to create adaptable CSR programmes that will enable them to respond to periods of political instability in Rivers State and perhaps other similar areas.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, political instability, community engagement, environmental sustainability, stakeholder theory, Niger Delta, Rivers State, moderated regression

INTRODUCTION

In many parts of sub-Saharan Africa that are rich in resources, but where politics are unstable, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become more than just a voluntary activity undertaken by companies. It is a significant mechanism for promoting community relations, mitigating conflict, and enhancing trust with the local community (Ebisi et al., 2025; Freeman, 1984). The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, especially Rivers State, is reckoned as one of the worst places to implement CSR. Despite making enough money from oil and gas production in the region,

the area is still rife with environmental degradation, fragile institutions, and restless communities (Uduji&Okolo-Obasi, 2021). Even though multinational oil and gas companies operating in the region have invested heavily in CSR schemes, the political instability is still a huge problem. Militant activities, communal conflicts, kidnapping, election- related violence and weak governance are some of the manifestations of this instability, which continue to plague the region (Obi, 2022).

The persistence of political instability in the Niger Delta, despite many years of CSR-related expenditures has increasingly become the focus of scholarly attention. This poses critical questions concerning the design, delivery and assessment of CSR interventions in conflict-affected communities (Obi,2022; Idemudia, 2022). Some scholars argue that models of good corporate social responsibility (CSR) developed for the well-established institutions of the Western world may not be relevant for the fragile institutions, political uncertainty and social instability in places like the Niger Delta (Idemudia, 2022; Frynas, 2005). In such contexts, CSR is not simply a voluntary activity companies undertake. It is frequently employed to create community relations, secure social license and deliver services in areas where governments might not sufficiently or effectively provide. Nonetheless, the success of such schemes may be influenced by local politics, inter-community conflicts and divergent interests, which potentially could impair their effectiveness and their consequences (Ebisi et al., 2025).

Several aspects of CSR such as corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability, ethical business conduct and community involvement have been well researched in the past. Yet, these elements have largely been conceptualized as separate with respect to their effects on development outcomes (Idemudia, 2022; Frynas, 2005). In addition, the degree to which political instability undermines CSR activity has received scant attention. This constitutes a significant gap in the literature because the political and social context in which CSR programs operate tends to shape them. As such, the present work investigates the direct effects of key CSR dimensions upon community and organizational outcomes, and also tests the moderating role of political instability across these relationships. Thus, by focusing on CSR in fragile and conflict-infused settings it feeds into relevant scholarly debates, while also offering practical guidance for those organizations who aim to develop more efficient CSR approaches in politically unstable contexts.

Statement of Problem and the Justification of the Study

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has increasingly become an essential strategic tool through which organizations contribute to the socio-economic development of their host communities. In regions characterized by resource extraction activities, particularly in oil-producing areas such as Rivers State, Nigeria, CSR initiatives are often expected to address developmental deficits, improve community welfare, reduce social tensions, and foster harmonious relationships between corporations and local stakeholders. Despite substantial investments in CSR programs by multinational oil companies and

other corporate organizations operating in Rivers State, the region continues to experience varying degrees of political instability manifested through communal conflicts, youth restiveness, militancy, political violence, protests, vandalism of oil facilities, and distrust between communities, corporations, and government institutions.

The persistence of these challenges raises concerns regarding the effectiveness of CSR initiatives in promoting political stability within host communities. While many corporations have implemented projects relating to education, healthcare, infrastructure development, environmental management, and youth empowerment, evidence suggests that these interventions have not always translated into sustainable peace and political stability. In many instances, communities perceive CSR programs as inadequate, poorly implemented, politically motivated, or lacking inclusiveness in decision-making processes. Such perceptions may exacerbate grievances, social exclusion, and conflicts rather than mitigate them.

Furthermore, existing empirical studies on CSR have predominantly focused on its effects on corporate performance, reputation, customer loyalty, employee satisfaction, and community development, with limited attention given to its influence on political stability, particularly within the context of oil-producing regions in developing economies. More importantly, the relationship between CSR and political stability is often treated as direct and linear, neglecting the possibility that contextual factors may strengthen or weaken this relationship. Variables such as community participation, government effectiveness, corporate transparency, stakeholder trust, and institutional quality may significantly moderate the impact of CSR on political stability.

In Rivers State, where socio-political tensions have historically been linked to issues of environmental degradation, resource control, unemployment, and perceived marginalization, there remains insufficient empirical evidence on the extent to which CSR contributes to political stability and how moderating variables influence this relationship. Consequently, a knowledge gap exists regarding the mechanisms through which CSR can effectively promote political stability in the region. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to examine the nexus between Corporate Social Responsibility and political stability in Rivers State, Nigeria, using moderated regression analysis to provide a more nuanced understanding of the relationship and the factors that influence it.

This study is justified on theoretical, empirical, practical, and policy grounds. From a theoretical perspective, the study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on Corporate Social Responsibility by extending the discourse beyond traditional organizational outcomes to examine its implications for political stability. The study enriches stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory, and social contract theory by exploring how corporate actions influence socio-political outcomes within host communities. By incorporating moderated regression analysis, the research provides a deeper understanding of the conditions under which CSR contributes to political stability.

Empirically, the study addresses a significant gap in the literature concerning the CSR–political stability relationship in Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State. Although numerous studies have investigated CSR practices in the Niger Delta region, few have specifically examined political stability as an outcome variable, and even fewer have employed advanced statistical techniques to analyze the moderating effects of contextual variables. The findings of this study will therefore provide empirical evidence that can enrich academic discourse and serve as a reference for future research.

Practically, the study will be beneficial to corporate organizations operating in Rivers State, especially multinational oil companies and other extractive industries. The findings will enable these organizations to design and implement CSR programs that are more responsive to community needs and capable of fostering trust, social cohesion, and political stability. Understanding the factors that moderate the relationship between CSR and political stability will help corporations allocate resources more effectively and improve stakeholder engagement strategies.

The study is also important to policymakers and government agencies responsible for community development, conflict management, and corporate regulation. The insights generated from the research will assist in formulating policies that encourage meaningful CSR practices and strengthen collaboration among corporations, communities, and government institutions. Such policies can contribute to reducing conflicts, enhancing governance, and promoting sustainable development in Rivers State and other resource-rich regions of Nigeria.

Additionally, host communities and civil society organizations will benefit from the study by gaining a better understanding of how CSR initiatives can be leveraged to promote peace, inclusiveness, and socio-political stability. The findings may encourage greater community participation in the planning and implementation of CSR projects, thereby improving their effectiveness and sustainability.

Ultimately, given the strategic economic importance of Rivers State and its history of socio-political unrest associated with resource extraction activities, investigating the nexus between Corporate Social Responsibility and political stability is both timely and necessary. The study will provide evidence-based recommendations for enhancing the role of CSR as a mechanism for promoting political stability, sustainable development, and peaceful coexistence among stakeholders in the region.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Among the key concepts of today's corporate governance, responsible management, business ethics and sustainable development is Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). CSR reflects an organization's promise to conduct its business in a responsible manner that considers its economic, social and environmental impacts. Businesses have

been under pressure to act in a socially responsible way to live up to four types of expectations: economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic (Carroll, 1991). The emergence of CSR signals a wider recognition that firms are not isolated entities, but are embedded in dense social, economic, political and ecological networks. This is because corporate activities inevitably affect the communities, institutions, natural resources and various stakeholders. Therefore, the ongoing shift toward broader benefit expectations can be observed from a changing business landscape and from evolving attitudes toward the purpose of business. LatapíAgudelo et al. (2019) point out CSR as an expression of an evolved 'social contract' with expectations beyond organizations merely seeking profits and actively engaging in 'the well-being of society'. Such a view is strongly supported as the ability to achieve long-term success is closely linked to its ability to maintain social legitimacy and acquire the confidence of its stakeholders. However, Friedman (1970) argued that the social responsibility of business is to increase its profits, and that the acceptance of those additional social responsibilities may lead to diminishing the business's efficiency and ultimately hamper the free market system itself.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is an expression of a firm's continuing dedication to responsible business conduct, positive societal outcomes, and reduction of negative environmental impacts, under pursuit of economic goals. CSR entails the integration of social, environmental and economic issues in a company's business operations and in its interaction with its stakeholders (Dahlsrud, 2008). Awa et al. (2024) further defines CSR as the incorporation of moral values, social responsibilities, environmental protection, and financial objectives in the business strategies to bring about a shared worth for firms and society. This means businesses need to consider the requirements and welfare of their employees, customers, local communities, governments, suppliers, and the generations they impact in the future. It is stressed by Ogbor et al. (2023) that CSR has become embedded in modern day business practices as ethical governance, responsible business practices and social accountability further strengthen long-term organizational sustainability and competitive advantage. It is a view that is gaining traction as organizations are increasingly being evaluated not based on financial results alone but also on their commitment to responsible conduct. However, some are skeptical that firms may use CSR as a façade of responsibility.

Concepts of corporate social responsibility (CSR) have changed over time. At first, CSR was most closely identified with corporate philanthropy, businesses giving back to society via donations, acts of charity and community involvement. This type of philanthropy involves non-compulsory corporate input into social issues, community welfare and development policies that transcend the boundaries of business objectives. Typical campaigns would be scholarships for schools, donations to hospitals, religious organizations and local infrastructure. But CSR today goes well beyond those philanthropic deeds, to social and environmental responsibility being embedded in how a company does its business. Contemporary CSR may be defined as the

integration of ethical, social, and environmental considerations into corporate policies, procedures, and practices within the business decision-making process on a sustained basis. Carroll and Brown (2018) claim the CSR has evolved from being a series of acts of individual corporate kindness to a holistic system that guides appropriate corporate behavior. Ogbor et al. (2023) align this view and argue CSR contributes to an organization's legitimacy and long-term, sustainable competitive advantage when accompanied by good governance and ethical principles. The change is well recognized, given that companies are now called upon to do more to address issues around environmental sustainability, employee welfare, ethical leadership, and community involvement, rather than just making infrequent charitable contributions.

A related and well-established conceptualization of CSR is the stakeholder theory. This view asserts that organizations have obligations not only to shareholders but also to anyone, including individuals, groups and institutions that are affected by its activities. Freeman (1984) defines stakeholders as individuals who can affect or are affected by the organization's achievement of its objectives, such as employees, customers, suppliers, investors, regulators and community. Harrison et al. (2015) argue that the theory calls for a consideration of competing interests as good business success depends on good relations with those who have some connection to the organization's business). Ogbor et al. (2023) argue that good corporate governance is inseparable from recognizing the interests of stakeholders and integrating moral reasoning in decisions of strategy. Such a view has become popular as organizations operate in complex networks and the support of stakeholders provides organizational stability, legitimacy, and long-term performance. However, its critics say the expectations of different stakeholder groups, which can be conflicting, will be difficult to manage.

Nowadays, CSR is closely linked with sustainability more than ever in the business world, where companies are required to deliver prosperity with protection of society and the environment. Sustainability has come to mean the capacity for meeting today's needs by organizations and/or communities in a manner that does not diminish the capacity for meeting needs by future generations. It may also means balancing social equity, economic vitality, and environmental quality to create sustainable progress in both organizations and communities. The concept is pinning down the idea that the short-term financial impact of the business' day-to-day operations is irrelevant when they have far longer term effects to consider. Elkington, (1997) introduced the triple bottom line framework which asserts that the success of an organization should be assessed against three pillars, namely: financial success, social responsibility and environmental sustainability. Bansal and DesJardine (2014) state that sustainable businesses are those that are focused on considerations such as long term rather than short term impacts on the environment, among other things. Ogbor et al. (2023) affirm this perspective by arguing that prudent management, CSR, and ethical behavior are fundamental instruments for realizing a sustainable competitive advantage. This is because as more companies realize that environmental responsibility and social integrity are essential to building sustainable

business models and competitive advantage. This view is becoming widely embraced. However, there are skeptics who argue that integrating profit and sustainability objectives continues to be difficult, particularly for companies operating in markets where competition is fierce and short-term financial pressure is intense.

Underpinning responsible organizational behavior is a fundamental concept of ethical the social responsibility to an organization is an important factor of organizational behavior. It is the business morality (principles and values) and how those underpin actions towards customers, suppliers, employees, partners and other stakeholders. It also seems to be the outcome of applying ethics in decision making about how to do business and manage employees, relate to customers, and connect with other stakeholders. These principles need to be balanced with respect for the particular circumstances of individual companies and the industry within which they operate. Ethics in business is the discipline which deals with making decisions regarding what is right or wrong in matters relating to the business. To conclude for Crane et al. (2019), business ethics provides the basis upon which you can decide what responsible or irresponsible behaviour within a specific organization is. Ethical theory is integral to interpreting CSR activities (Mohr et al., 2001), CSR derives its real meaning through an organization's ethical conduct (Schwartz, 2017), and it is the ethical conduct of the other party that defines what this responsibility entails (Dahlsrud, 2008). Ogbor et al. (2023) emphasize the interrelation of ethics and CSR as ethical means equate to having CSR within them and long term sustainability cannot be furthered by moral means and unethical ends regardless of amplitude of a benevolent acts of philanthropy. They stress that ethics and CSR must be integrated because the former serves as the guiding principle of the later. This is a popular-point view: without real ethical underpinning CSR can too easily be co-opted into the public relations armory rather than being an expression of true responsibility. Nevertheless, for some companies, CSR is still viewed as a separate issue from their broader ethical obligations, raising questions about the sincerity of their social involvement.

Corporate governance is a fundamental aspect of corporate social responsibility (CSR), as responsible business requires responsible business leadership and management. It refers to the system of rules, practices, and processes by which a company is directed and controlled. It is also the set of processes, mechanisms and relations by which a company is operated and controlled that makes it easy to maintain transparency, equality, responsibility and good decision making as a business. Good corporate governance enables an organization to meet the expectations of its stakeholders and is widely recognized as the best means of doing this in a sustainable and ethical manner. It describes the way power should be exercised within the corporate firm and how responsibilities should be divided among executives, boards, shareholders and other stakeholders (2019). Strong governance improves accountability and results in better organizational performance. Mallin (2019) also confirms a symbiotic relationship between corporate governance, CSR and ethics, indicating that an efficient governance structure serves as the base for companies to adopt responsible practices and hold on to competitive advantage. This is a well-supported opinion,

as bad governance leads to corruption, lack of accountability and exploitation of its stakeholders. Even these governance structures, however, can fail to ensure ethical conduct if the organization culture does not support integrity and ethical conduct.

The concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become increasingly important in modern business as organizations are now operating in societies that are placing growing demands on them to become more accountable and ethical. CSR may be described as a strategic concept that allows companies to address their social and environmental responsibilities and at the same time creates value for stakeholders and improves the company's overall performance. In another sense, CSR is proposed as the integration of ethical behavior in the business process that can be the source of organizational profit, as well as in providing positive outcomes in the society. Today companies use CSR to build brand, deepen stakeholder engagement, reduce risk, and gain competitive advantage. CSR activities build corporate reputation and create a stronger bond with its stakeholders, Jo and Harjoto (2012) argued. In the same way, Khan et al. (2013) found that investors and consumers are now increasingly considering the social and environmental performance of corporations when they look at the credibility of corporations. Ismail et al. (2023) further posit responsible corporate performance leads to sustainable competitive advantage through the building of trust, legitimacy and long-term stakeholder engagement. This view has substantial support, as responsible organizations normally receive more public trust and higher visibility in the market place. However, there are also critiques saying that efforts of CSR could lead to higher operational costs, particularly for companies in the developing world where resources are limited.

The Community Development CSR is an essential factor of the community development, since the organizations are in general dealing with socio-abilities, which are the communities that are affected by their activity. Community development, therefore, is a combination of top-down and bottom-up strategies to bring about social, economic and environmental well-being through community action, investment, and support. CSR activities within communities can be thought of as corporate initiatives addressing specific local requirements, advancing education, providing better healthcare, developing infrastructure, generating employment, and rolling out poverty-reduction measures. When companies participate in such national and international affairs, they are reminded of their common interests with the cities and regions in which they operate, and thus contribute to solving social and developmental problems there. Aguinis and Glavas (2012) suggest that CSR facilitates firms to create social value, which in turn helps building relations with stakeholders. Wang et al. (2016) also state that CSR legitimizes the organization because people tend to support companies which contribute to social good. Ogbor et al. (2023) state that ethical corporate conduct enhances corporate legitimacy, yielding long-term competitive advantage when such positive interaction with the environment is maintained. This way of seeing things is particularly pertinent in many developing countries where the public sector may be unable to satisfy societal expectations to the fullest extent. Yet

CSR is to be complementary to and not a substitute for government role.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is considered essential in promoting the protection of the environment, as enterprises are now under more pressure to reduce the negative environmental effects of their activities. Environmental responsibility is an organization's responsibility to limit environmental damage, conserve natural resources, reduce pollution and to carry on with sustainable manufacturing and operating procedures. Alternatively, environmental CSR can be construed as corporate efforts to protect ecosystems while making sure that business practices comply with environmental stewardship. This dimension of CSR has found an increased attention in light of growing concerns regarding climate change, environmental degradation, loss of biodiversity, pollution, overexploitation of natural resources. Therefore, enterprises are required to involve into waste mitigation, energy conservation, emission management, resource saving and green manufacturing, etc. As stated by Eccles et al. (2014), sustainability-oriented firms are argued to be more likely to achieve superior long term performance, as implementation of environmentally responsible practices may not only bring operational efficiency, but also improvement in the reputation and the trust of stakeholders. Fatemi et al. (2018) also state that stakeholders judge companies by their environmental actions and perceive these to be manifestations of sincere commitment to doing business ethically. Ogbor et al. (2023) argue that environmental responsibility is a core aspect of good corporate governance, especially for companies that seek to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage by considering the environmental consequences of their activities. This way of thinking has become popular as world environmental problems intensify bringing greater pressure on organizations to conduct themselves as socially responsible entities. However, some critics warn that environmental CSR can place additional financial strain, especially on those companies that have to invest heavily in sustainable technologies and practices.

The importance of corporate social responsibility (CSR) is getting more pronounced in the context of society with socio-political and economic challenges. This instability usually entails weak institutions, uncertain politics, economic strains, social unrest, and lacking of governance, all of which act as barriers to development and good security. It can also be defined as a situation where institutional weakness and rising social demands limit the ability of nations and institutions to make sustained progress. It is in these unstable environments that business is conducted and companies are trying to make a living, doing so in places such as where poverty and joblessness are endemic, where insecurity is pervasive, where environmental devastation is so widespread, and the supply of public goods is weakest. CSR provides companies with the latitude to nurture social stability through the way they conduct their business in an ethical manner, engage meaningfully with stakeholders and/or invest in community development via focused interventions. Ushie and Kekung (2024) argue governance challenges and profound socio-economic adversity undermine efforts at development and increase insecurity and societal friction. In the words of the International Business Leaders Forum (2007), CSR is about responsible engagement of companies in "giving back" to their own communities and in contributing to sustainable development. Ogbor et al. (2023) further posit

that ethical governance in conjunction with strong CSR practices contributes to firms' ability to gain trust, improve stakeholder relations and maintain legitimacy in even the most unfavorable conditions. This notion is generally endorsed as wholesome corporate behavior can abate conflict, strengthen community ties, and lead to a more supportive business climate. Still, CSR cannot be a substitute for strong government institutions, for commerce by itself will not address the root structural causes of instability.

Furthermore, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is vital to the enhancement of both organizational legitimacy and competitive advantage. Legitimacy refers to the general perception or assumption that the actions of an organization are desirable, proper, or appropriate within the norms and expectations of the social system in which it operates. Sustainable competitive advantage is also defined as the firm's ability to deliver greater value to its customers than that of the competitors by engaging unique resources, capabilities and ethical conduct. The integrity of an organization, the engagement with its stakeholders and the responsiveness to societal needs is increasingly regarded as sources of competitive advantage by a number of today's organizations. CSR creates shared value when companies address social problems and, at the same time, enhance their operational value, maintained Porter and Kramer (2011). This is complemented by Ogbor et al. (2023) who stress that CSR and corporate governance as well as good ethics, form a triangle of sustainability capable of transcending traditional models that are based on pure resource holds. This perspective is widely accepted because companies that have more responsible relationships with their stakeholders are likely to have better reputations, more loyal customers, and a longer life span. Still others warn that CSR is being co-opted, that real responsibility requires a commitment that goes beyond the self-serving interests of organizations.

The interconnectedness between corporate social responsibility (CSR), ethics, governance, and sustainability indicates that responsible business behavior is not simply about engaging in isolated social responsibility activities. Real responsible management is about integrating ethical decision making, stakeholder dialogue, environmental responsibility, and social responsibility into the fabric of an organization's management processes. Those who truly practice CSR are anticipated to demonstrate accountability not just internally to their direct operations but also in how they engage with stakeholders and the impact on society more generally. Certainly, "the success of CSR depends on the integration of the corporate governance, ethical conduct, and sustainable business practice as these determinants reflect the reputation and the sustainable business of an organization," as Ogbor et al. (2023) accentuate. This perspective is widely supported, because CSR initiatives become more meaningful when they are based in transparent governance, principled leadership, and institutional commitment, rather than being conducted as short-term, adhoc efforts. However, debate continues as to whether voluntary CSR commitments are sufficient or if enhanced regulatory frameworks are required to institutionalize corporate accountability.

In summary, corporate responsibility (CSR) is an economic, social, and environmental concept that businesses

need to consider when achieving their economic objectives. It involves the integration of ethical conduct, stakeholder engagement, environmental behavior, social responsibility and sustainability within the organization and in business practice. Indeed, CSR has progressed over time from a narrow focus on philanthropy to a comprehensive approach that impacts power relations within governance of the corporation and in its decisions affecting corporate realities of mission, ethics, sustainability, community connection, and ultimately organizational effectiveness. CSR is said to include various intertwined types of responsibilities (Carroll, 1991) and stakeholder interests are considered fundamental in this type of decision making (Freeman, 1984). Ogbor et al. (2023) posit that firms attain sustainable competitive advantages through CSR activities when these are supported by good governance, ethical leadership, and responsible management. This point of view is very much in line with the foundational principles of trust, legitimacy and accountability that underwrite the sustainability of modern organizations. Yet as CSR is still developing, there are ongoing discussions about the most appropriate balance between the voluntary corporate activities on one hand and on the other financial interests and legal obligations.

Social responsibility, stakeholder dynamics, and political instability in the Niger Delta

Conceptually, this research enables the understanding of the link between CSR activity and its effect on the community and the organizational performance in the context of political instability in Rivers State, Nigeria. It is grounded in Stakeholder Theory developed by Freeman (1984). This approach says that the interests and needs of all parties impacted by an organization's actions must be considered by the organization. The theory posits that an organization's long-term viability and legitimacy is reliant upon its management of relationships with key stakeholders including host communities, employees, government agencies, regulators, investors and civil society organizations.

In the Niger Delta, the dynamics of consultation between stakeholders are so complex that multinational oil and gas companies find it difficult to engage with indigenous peoples who bear the brunt of environmental destruction, unemployment, abject poverty, weak governance and chronic political chaos (Idemudia, 2022). Hence CSR has moved from being a technique for voluntary philanthropy to a strategic tool of conflict resolution, legitimacy construction, stakeholder management, and control mechanism for operational survival (Ebisi et al., 2025). Drawing on stakeholder theory and resource dependence theory, the proposed model views CSR as a multi-faceted concept underpinned by four independent constructs consisting of corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability programmes, ethical practices and community involvement. These dimensions were chosen because they are the prevailing CSR techniques employed by multinational corporations operating in oil-producing communities in Rivers State and have been identified as vital factors influencing corporate integrity and stakeholder satisfaction by CSR studies (Carroll, 1991; Oyesomo et al., 2024).

Corporate philanthropy is when a business donates time or resources to causes or organizations to help its community, such as awarding scholarships, contributing to infrastructure projects, making donations, providing health services or backing programmes that empower youth. This is also one of the major forms of CSR in the Niger Delta. However, scholars caution that such forms of philanthropy may result only in temporary benefits when not embedded in sustainable development agendas that enable long-term community advances (Ite, 2024). Environmental sustainability practices are an organization's efforts to minimize air and water pollution to protect the environment. They include pollution control, oil spill cleanup, restoration of the environment, managing resources sustainably. Environmental accountability is key in the Rivers State, due to the fact that the communities are suffering from environmental pollution as a result of crude extraction, which has been basis for agitations, social unrest, and mistrust for multinational corporations (Aye-Agele et al., 2025).

Ethical conduct, in this context, relates to specifications of how companies conduct business with stakeholders, including undertaking projects, labour relations and conducting governance systems, in a way that is transparent, accountable and fair. In fact, corporate ethical governance is recognized as a significant determinant of CSR effectiveness, as communities often assess the legitimacy of a firm by the level of integrity, honesty, and accountability that it portrays within its practices (Erin et al., 2021). In unstable political environments, unethical practices such as corruption, the manipulation of community representatives, and the fraying of CSR benefits along ethnic lines can exacerbate tensions and undermine social cohesion. Community involvement is now considered to be a core element of the participatory mechanism through which companies and host communities interact in identifying development needs, designing corporate social responsibility (CSR) interventions, resolving grievances, and monitoring project application. Research indicates that engagement with the community is one of the most significant predictors of social license to operate because participatory CSR models sustain stakeholder trust, mitigate hostility and contribute positively to the sustainability of projects (Dare et. al., 2014; Uduji&Okolo-Obasi, 2021).

The outcome variable under consideration is the co-impact of community and organizational results. Community impact can be understood as the beneficial alteration that direct outcomes of CSR programs have in host communities in socio-welfare, community satisfaction, peace building and development indicators. Organizational performance is the degree to which an organization is doing well in terms of its operational viability, corporate image, stakeholder collaboration and sustainable business in the long run. Research suggests that companies that pursue CSR more effectively tend to have superior stakeholder relations, less operational disruption, increased legitimacy, and potentially enhanced organizational performance (Kaplan & Norton, 1992). The variable of political instability is integrated into the model as a moderating variable as when the political and institutional context is less stable, it may be more difficult to implement CSR strategies. Political instability prevails in Rivers State through the likes of militancy, communal crises, electoral violence, kidnapping, cultism, bad government and

insecurity (Okolie& Wilson, 2023). These difficulties may also diminish the effectiveness of CSR efforts by halting execution processes, restricting stakeholder participation, raising skepticism, and compelling organizations to allocate more resources to crisis management and security efforts.

The political instability as a moderating effect suggests that the positive impacts of even the best CSR instruments can be limited in an environment of continuous insecurity and failing governance. Ebisi et al. (2025) contended that CSR models based on politically stable contexts are not always transferable to conflict-affected areas as they do not take into account the destabilizing influence of insecurity on relations with stakeholders and the delivery of the programme. Hence, this study presumes a strong effect of political instability on the magnitude and direction of the relationship between the dimensions of CSR and organizational/community performance.

Thus, the theoretical model predicts that corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability, ethical good-business-practice, political instability and community involvement would all positively relate to community impact and organizational performance and that political instability would interfere in the above constructs positively or negatively in the Rivers State context in a negative manner, thus, exacerbating, or mitigating the influence of CSR activities in Rivers state.

The model treats CSR as a multi-faceted concept with four dimensions: philanthropy (CP), environmental sustainability (CESI), ethical practices (CEP) and community engagement (CCE) and considers political instability (PI) as a moderating variable in the relation between each CSR dimension and the composite dependent variable, which is community impact and organizational performance (Y). In Figure 1, the conceptual model is illustrated.

Figure 1.

Conceptual Framework: Moderated Effects of CSR Dimensions on Community Impact and Organisational Performance in a Politically Unstable Environment. Note. CP = Corporate Philanthropy; CESI = Environmental Sustainability Initiatives; CEP = Ethical Practices; CCE = Community Engagement; PI = Political Instability (moderator); Y = Community Impact / Organisational Performance.

2.2 Theoretical review

This research is based on Stakeholder Theory, which was introduced by R. Edward Freeman (1984). The theory posit that corporates bodies owe duties not only to its shareholders but to all people and entities, which are impacted by its actions or that may affect its operations. In Rivers State, these actors are the host communities, militant youth groups, traditional rulers, government agencies, international NGOs, and investors. The theory explains how organizations design and deliver their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes. It indicates that firms generally target their CSR activities at stakeholder segments whose expressed concerns and potential influence are perceived as essential for the continued smooth running of the company. Hence, CSR becomes an instrument for managing relationships with stakeholders, mobilizing the support of the community, and mitigating threats that could potentially interrupt one’s business (Mitchell et al., 1997).

Stakeholder Theory has particular pertinence in the context of political instability as instability is liable to alter the balance of power and significance among various stakeholders. In times of strife, non-state entities such as armed groups can gain strength, and traditional leadership and government structures may find themselves less able to respond to the needs of their constituencies. Consequently, the range of stakeholders involved may Broaden and the need to negotiate with them to keep peace and for the survival of their organization might become necessary (Tamuno, 2022). Hence, the theory not only accounts for the undertakings of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in organizations but also suggests that the success of such activities is largely dependent on the political context in which these activities are carried out. In regions of political upheaval, CSR initiatives might be less successful as the instability, insecurity, and absence of effective governance could inhibit their desired effect.

2.3 Empirical review

2.3.1 Corporate Philanthropy and Community Outcomes

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), such as donations, scholarships, community infrastructure provision, and social amenities delivery, is arguably the most practised and visible aspect of CSR in the Niger Delta (Olawuyi&Nwosu, 2023). Whether it can deliver sustainable benefits for the host community, however, remains contentious. Gbali et al. (2021) investigating CSR and conflict management in Niger Delta community found that philanthropy related activities were deeply sporadic state driven politics within such behaviour was exploitative and political influenced. Thus these efforts did little to mitigate tensions between community and Oil Company, or to build long-term community satisfaction. Alaburo et al. (2023) reported that corporate philanthropy is the weakest predictor of community resilience among environmental sustainability and ethical practices using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). Their findings suggest that charity and one-off assistance do not alleviate poverty, underdevelopment or social exclusion in oil-producing communities.

Olawuyi and Nwosu(2023) examined the relationship between corporate philanthropy and sustainable community development in the Niger-Delta region employing a survey research design. The data was gathered by means of structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview schedules administered to community leaders, youth representatives, and corporate relations officers who were purposively selected. The results showed that philanthropic CSR (such as donations, scholarships and community projects) gave immediate gains for host communities by meeting acute social problems. On the contrary, it is observed that these policies have minimal influence on chronic problems such as unemployment, environmental deterioration and poverty alleviation. Corporate philanthropy, although found to positively impact community welfare, was considered too limited a means to the end of community development and hence sustainable development. The researchers thus recommended that multinational corporations should integrate philanthropic programmes with sustainable development activities such as vocational training, livelihood support schemes, and local economic empowerment programmes to guarantee that the benefits to host communities are lasting.

Mbachu and Mbachu (2024) examined the influence of corporate generosity on the restiveness of the youth in oil producing communities in rivers state, with questionnaires serving as the major instrument for data collection from the youths and other community stakeholders. The study employed both purposive and simple random sampling techniques to select participants. The results indicated that ill-conceived philanthropic corporate social responsibility programmes (CSRs) were of little assistance in mitigating the problems of youth unemployment and insecurity. In view of the findings, the researchers proposed the adoption of strategic youth empowerment schemes, support for entrepreneurship schemes, and continuous stakeholder involvement as more helpful and sustainable measures vis-a-vis sporadic gifts and welfare aid.

Reinforcing this point of view, Ite (2021) has characterized numerous philanthropic CSR interventions in oil-producing regions as “pacification philanthropy,” reactive strategies designed to perpetuate momentary peace rather than fostering sustained community growth. The researcher suggested that such interventions could also exacerbate tensions within communities when benefit distribution is considered to be unjust or politically motivated. In the same manner, Idemudia (2022) maintains that the predominate philanthropic CSR approach in Rivers State tends to generate dependency relations

within community dwellers and undermines prospects for authentic empowerment which makes it less likely to lead to sustainable social and economic transformation.

2.3.2 Environmental Sustainability and Community Trust

Environmental sustainability is among the most significant and heavily contested aspects of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) within the extractive sector, particularly because the means of survival for several Niger Delta communities are intimately linked to land and water (Uduji&Okolo-Obasi, 2021). Aye-Agele et al. (2025), utilizing an analytical survey method, studied environmental CSR practices in the petroleum-producing communities of the Niger Delta. The examination revealed that, despite the assertions of corporations that they are environmentally responsible, many communities remained plagued by neglect such as oil spills, gas flaring, and slow or non-existent clean-up efforts. The respondents interpreted these conditions as indicating that numerous environmental CSR programs were shallow, and that the true environmental worries of those communities suffering from the greatest environmental harm were not being tackled. It was concluded that the disjuncture between corporate environmental rhetoric and community narratives of experience serves to alienate communities, undermine corporate credibility and escalate tensions in the region.

Ovie-D'Leone and Abolaji (2024) reinforced these findings in similar studies through participant observation and document analysis in oil-producing communities in Rivers State. The research revealed that environmental CSR activities are thus far relatively unproductive due to poor monitoring mechanisms, weak enforcement of environmental laws, and political meddling in environmental remediation procedures. The scholars noted that although corporations asserted they were being environmentally responsible, many communities still suffered from oil pollution and environmental harm. These are in tandem with the UNEP (2011) evaluation that showed a vast divergence between corporate environmental pledges and the realities on the ground in Ogoni land. Similarly, Kadafa (2022) accounted for the persistence of gas flaring and substandard clean-up measures in host communities. It was further implied that the effectiveness of environmental CSRs to impact positively on environmental protection, community trust and conflict prevention in such environments with weak institutions and political turmoil is questionable.

Kadafa (2022) examined environmental pollution and remediation issue in the Niger Delta in which the methods used were documentary analysis and cross sectional analysis. Information regarding the subject matter was conducted using a sample of environmental experts and community residents. The study employed a purposive sampling method to identify communities polluted by the environment. The result showed that gas flaring had been continuous, oil spills were common and clean up mechanisms were weak, all of which caused environmental concerns and distrust for multinational companies based in the region among community members. The research also found that poor enforcement of environmental regulations and slow remediation efforts exacerbated the environmental and socio-economic conditions of community hosts. On the strength of the findings, the investigator called for introduction of sterner penalties for environmental violations, enhancement of environmental compliance and monitoring systems, promoting investment in environmentally sustainable technologies and pollution abatements to ensure environmental sustainability and restoring community confidence.

Nwankwo and Eze (2024) investigated Environmental Responsibility and Community relations in oil-producing in Rivers State. The study employed a survey research design and data was collected using a structured questionnaire from residents of environmentally impacted communities. A stratified random sampling method was applied to achieve balance representation

of various stakeholders within the study location. Results indicated that communities with severe environmental deterioration had significantly lower trust and confidence in foreign multinationals operating in their regions. Poor environmental management practices within corporate- community relations also diminished stakeholder support for corporate endeavours, the research demonstrated. Consequently, the researchers urged multinational corporations to institutionalize environmental impact assessments, mainstream participatory environmental monitoring process with community members and integrate community-inclusive remediation models to bolster corporate legitimacy, environmental accountability and stakeholder trust.

2.3.3 Ethical Practices and Corporate Legitimacy

Transparency, accountability, anti-corruption compliance, fair contracting and equal treatment of stakeholders, which constitute good practices, are essential elements that influence the perception of the community on integrity and credibility of corporations in the success of their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes (Adegboyega&Akinlabi, 2022). Victor (2022) investigated the contribution of ethical engagement to CSR realization among phenomenological interviewees considered community leaders located in Rivers State. This led to the determination that community approval and support for CSR initiatives can be directly linked to the transparency to which a community project is enacted, honesty in delivering messages and the sense of equitability within a community when making decisions. Results also indicated that non-ethical issues such as non-transparency and inequitably sharing rewards also created a sense of distrust within the community and undermined even those CSR programmes that were well-financed. The study therefore inferred from the findings that ethical principles must be applied in order to fashion positive corporate-community relations and ensure CSR interventions' long term success.

Oluwaseun and Ibrahim (2024) investigated the impact of ethical leadership on the sustainability of organizations in the Nigerian oil and gas sector. The research was a survey type design and data were collected by distributing questionnaires to the employees, the management and the representatives of the host community. A combination of purposive and random multistage sampling procedure was applied in selecting the respondents. Results showed that ethical disclosure positively influences the stakeholders' trust, operational stability and performance of the organization. The study also revealed that organizations perceived as being more ethical were perceived as having greater stakeholder support and stronger corporate reputations. Drawing upon these results, they advocated, inter alia, to reinforce corporate legitimacy, the improvement of stakeholder relations, and the promotion of long-term organizational sustainability by adopting regular ethics training programmes, protection policies for whistleblowers, comprehensive anti-corruption measures, and more stringent monitoring, and enforcement of compliance.

Victor and Akaneme (2022) analyzed the effect of unethical CSR practices on conflict manifestation in Rivers State. The research used qualitative approach and data were collected through in-depth interviews and analysis of conflict events with community leaders, youth groups, and civil society organizations. Using their knowledge and experience of the CSR-related conflicts in the region, participants were chosen through purposive sampling. Findings indicated that unethical behavior including the manipulation of community representatives, non-transparency, secrecy in decision making, and inequitable allocation of CSR benefits fueled distrust, anger, and animosity against multinational corporations. The study also revealed that such practices undermined corporate-community relations and spurred conflicts in host communities. On the basis of these results, the researchers suggest transparent systems of governance, the fair and equitable allocation of the resources of

corporate social responsibility, and inclusive stakeholder accountability system as means to build trust, improve community relations and mitigate the risk of conflict.

2.3.4 Community Engagement and Social Licence to Operate

Community engagement is the way that corporations and community members connect, consult and collaborate with one another in developing and delivering community projects. It is considered the most significant aspect of the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as it enables the organization to obtain and retain the support and acceptance from the community for its continued existence (Ojo&Ite, 2023). Uduji and Okolo-Obasi (2021) interrogated community engagement strategies in the Niger Delta and demonstrated that top-down strategies, those that excluded communities from decision making, were an abject failure. The research demonstrated that such non-inclusive models often negates valid community leadership structures, emboldens armed youth groups, and erodes indigenous governance structures. Hence, they often fail to bring desired results and increasingly serve to fuel alienation in host communities. It was recommended that corporations should develop engagement models, which are inclusive and involve the community as a stakeholder at every point of project planning, execution and delivery.

Victor (2022) analyzed community influence over CSR decision-making through qualitative interviews with community members and leaders from Rivers State. Results indicated that communities that were involved in participatory planning and decision-making were more positive towards CSR initiatives, had greater trust in corporations, and experienced lower levels of stress and conflict, even when the projects were of high financial value. Similarly, Gbali et al. (2021) established that participatory monitoring of CSR initiatives enhanced community satisfaction and mitigated tensions between corporations and community hosts. The research suggested that it is the nature of community involvement (particularly that it is inclusive, transparent, representative and iteratively consultative), rather financial worth, that determines CSR success.

Tamuno (2022) critically examined CSR in the Niger Delta through documentary analysis complemented by qualitative interviews with corporate managers, government officials, and community stakeholders. The purposive sampling technique was used as participants had the expert knowledge in the area under study. The results revealed inadequate stakeholder participation and governance structures that undermined the efficacy of the CSR programmes, despite significantly corporate funds. It was found that the non-collaborative manner in which key stakeholders pursued development initiatives compromised their sustainability. The researcher therefore concluded by advocating for a collaborative governance model partnership of corporations, governments, civil society organizations and host communities as a means to aid accountability and sustainable development for better outcomes.

Olaniyan and Ipinnaiye (2026) explored the sustainability of regional development within the context of the Niger Delta through qualitative interviews, policy analysis and stakeholder engagement with local communities as well as development practitioners. Purposive and snowball sampling were used to select participants who have adequate knowledge about the phenomenon. The results suggested that top-down CSR and development approaches can fail spectacularly because they misread local realities, community demands, and exclude the participation of stakeholders. From the present study, it can be conclusively drawn that the sustainable development is easily attainable with the participation of local community in decision making. The authors thus advocate for collaborative governance models that integrate institutionalized support with community-based participation and innovation.

Abiodun(2023) researched on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and human rights in Nigeria's post-amnesty Niger Delta through qualitative interviews and secondary documentary materials sourced from community representatives, non-governmental organizations, and policy institutions. Participants were chosen through purposive sampling, as they had the most direct experiences with CSR and human rights matters. Results showed that the failure to adequately enforce CSR requirements was a major contributor to insecurity, youth demonstrations, community discontent, and human rights abuses in the area. The study showed that the poor CSR management contributes towards distrust among the community, and escalation of social unrest. The author called for transparent CSR governance models, sustainable youth empowerment initiatives, more robust human rights compliance instruments and greater community participation as the best means to support peace and development in the Niger Delta.

3.0 Methodology

This study employed the descriptive survey research design to evaluate the efficiency of CSR programmes under political risk conditions. The study population consisted of 300 participants belonging to three key stakeholder categories in Rivers State: Multinational oil and gas companies' employees, host communities and local government officials. Stratified random sampling, a sample of 250 respondents was drawn to obtain adequate representation of each cohort. The sample consisted of 100 employees of the corporate, 120 members of the host community and 30 representatives of local government.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed on the basis of the key variables of the study, i.e., corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability practices, ethical practice, community involvement, political instability, and community impact/organizational performance. The Questionnaire was divided into six subsections, each one composed of five statements linked to a specific construct. Subsequently, the participants were required to indicate their agreement with each statement by ticking one of the five response options (Liker scale; 1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree). The survey questions draw on concepts and measures taken from prior studies in the areas of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and stakeholder management. To enhance content validity, the instrument was evaluated by three management science and corporate governance experts. In addition, a pilot test with 30 participants outside the main study area was also conducted to test the reliability of the instrument. The findings yielded Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients ranging from 0.76 to 0.84 which were in excess of the recommended minimum value of 0.70 signifying that the questionnaire was reliable and appropriate to be used for the collection of data.

The data were analyzed with IBM SPSS Statistics 27. Descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation were used to describe responses of respondents. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was applied to assess the relationships among the variables under study. Also, the hypotheses were tested via moderated multiple regression procedures to assess the moderating effects of political instability in the relations of CSR dimensions with community impact/organizational performance. The significance level was set at 0.05 for all statistical tests, and the results were reported with appropriate statistical indicators along with the effect sizes.

4.0 Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of all the study variables. Political instability had the highest mean ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.95$), which corroborated the respondents' strong view that the political environment in Rivers State was one of political volatility. In terms of CSR aspects, ethical practices had the highest mean ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 0.78$), followed by corporate philanthropy ($M = 3.41$, $SD = 0.82$), community participation ($M = 3.29$, $SD = 0.88$), and environmental sustainability ($M = 3.18$, $SD = 0.91$). The outcome, community impact and organizational performance, had a modestly lower mean ($M = 3.07$, $SD = 0.97$), revealing moderate CSR effectiveness. Skewness values of ± 1.0 with kurtosis value of 2.5–3.5 indicate that approximate normality was found for all variables.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables (N = 250)

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Corporate Philanthropy (CP)	250	3.41	0.82	1.00	5.00	-0.22	2.87
Environmental Sustainability (CESI)	250	3.18	0.91	1.00	5.00	-0.15	2.71
Ethical Practices (CEP)	250	3.56	0.78	1.00	5.00	-0.31	3.12
Community Engagement (CCE)	250	3.29	0.88	1.00	5.00	-0.19	2.94
Political Instability (PI)	250	3.72	0.95	1.00	5.00	-0.41	3.28
Community Impact / Org. Performance (Y)	250	3.07	0.97	1.00	5.00	-0.08	2.68

Note. SD = Standard Deviation. All variables measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). Skewness and kurtosis values indicate approximate normality.

4.2 Pearson Correlation Analysis

Table 2 shows the Pearson correlations of all variables in this study. All four dimensions of CSR were positively and significantly associated with community impact and organizational performance: CP ($r = .48$, $p < .01$), CESI ($r = .41$, $p < .01$), CEP ($r = .55$, $p < .01$), as well as CCE ($r = .53$, $p < .01$). Political instability was negatively and significantly correlated with all CSR dimensions ($r = -.29$ to $-.38$) as well as with the dependent variable ($r = -.43$), indicating that it was an adverse moderating factor. The positive inter-correlations of the four CSR dimensions ($r = .44$ to $.58$) also suggest conceptual convergence and are well below the recommended cut-off for multicollinearity of $r = .80$. Figure 2 is a scatter plot matrix: bivariate relationships are depicted between CSR dimensions and community impact. **Table 2** Pearson Correlation Matrix for Study Variables (N = 250)

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Corporate Philanthropy (CP)	1.00					
2. Env't. Sustainability (CESI)	.44**	1.00				
3. Ethical Practices (CEP)	.51**	.49**	1.00			
4. Community Engagement (CCE)	.46**	.52**	.58**	1.00		
5. Political Instability (PI)	-.31**	-.38**	-.29**	-.35**	1.00	
6. Community Impact / Org. Perf. (Y)	.48**	.41**	.55**	.53**	-.43**	1.00

Note. ** $p < .01$ (two-tailed). Values in bold represent correlations with the dependent variable (Community Impact / Organisational Performance).

Figure 2. Scatter Plot Matrix Illustrating Bivariate Relationships Between CSR Dimensions (CP, CESI, CEP, CCE) and Community Impact/Organisational Performance (Y), with Political Instability (PI) overlaid as a shading variable.

4.3 Moderated Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 3 shows the results of the moderated multiple regression. The full model was significant, $F(9, 240) = 27.84, p < .001$, and it accounted for 51.2% of the variance in community impact and organizational performance ($R^2 = .512$, Adjusted $R^2 = .493$). 1) All four dimensions of CSR were found to positively and significantly predict community and organizational results: recently, CEP ($\beta = .32, t = 4.67, p < .001$) and CCE ($\beta = .27, t = 3.83, p < .001$) had the strongest effects, followed by CP ($\beta = .22, t = 3.17, p = .002$) and CESI ($\beta = .17, t = 2.00, p = .047$). Directly, political instability was a negative but positive advocated direct determinant of ($\beta = -.21, t = -3.60, p < .001$), its negative impact of it on CSR results was established even without considering moderation.

Three of the four interaction terms were significant, indicating that political instability moderated: $CP \times PI$ ($\beta = -.12, t =$

-2.25, $p = .025$), $CEP \times PI$ ($\beta = -.14$, $t = -2.75$, $p = .006$), and $CCE \times PI$ ($\beta = -.16$, $t = -3.25$, $p = .001$). The $CESI \times PI$ interaction tended toward significance, but did not reach conventional levels ($\beta = -.09$, $t = -1.75$, $p = .081$). The significant interaction effect for political stability means that political instability consistently diminishes the potency of philanthropy, ethics, and community relations as predictors of positive community and organizational results. Figure 3 presents the simple slope analysis of the interaction of PI with community involvement on community influence when PI is high and low.

Table 3 Moderated Multiple Regression Results: Effects of CSR Dimensions and Political Instability on Community Impact/Organizational Performance (N = 250)

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	P	95% CI [Lower]	95% CI [Upper]
Constant	0.51	0.21	—	2.43	.015	0.10	0.92
Corporate Philanthropy (CP)	0.19	0.06	.22	3.17	.002	0.07	0.31
Env. Sustainability (CESI)	0.14	0.07	.17	2.00	.047	0.00	0.28
Ethical Practices (CEP)	0.28	0.06	.32	4.67	<.001	0.16	0.40
Community Engagement (CCE)	0.23	0.06	.27	3.83	<.001	0.11	0.35
Political Instability (PI) — Moderator	-0.18	0.05	-.21	-3.60	<.001	-0.28	-0.08
CP \times PI	-0.09	0.04	-.12	-2.25	.025	-0.17	-0.01
CESI \times PI	-0.07	0.04	-.09	-1.75	.081	-0.15	0.01
CEP \times PI	-0.11	0.04	-.14	-2.75	.006	-0.19	-0.03
CCE \times PI	-0.13	0.04	-.16	-3.25	.001	-0.21	-0.05

$R^2 = .512$; Adjusted $R^2 = .493$; $F(9, 240) = 27.84$, $p < .001$; ΔR^2 for interaction terms = .048

Note. B = unstandardised regression coefficient; SE = standard error; β = standardised coefficient; CI = confidence interval. All continuous predictors were mean-centred prior to computation of interaction terms. $R^2 = .512$; Adjusted $R^2 = .493$; $F(9, 240) = 27.84$, $p < .001$. ΔR^2 for interaction terms = .048, $p < .05$.

Figure 3.

Interaction Effect of Political Instability (PI) on the Relationship Between Community Engagement (CCE) and Community Impact/Organisational Performance (Y). Note. Simple slopes plotted at ± 1 SD from the mean of PI. High PI significantly attenuates the positive effect of community engagement on community impact.

4.4 Discussion

The results from the research indicates that the four aspects of CSR; corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability programs, ethical practices, and community engagement positively influence on community affect and corporate implementation in Rivers State, Nigeria. According to the findings, ethical practices ($\beta = .32, p < .001$) and community engagement ($\beta = .27, p < .001$) exerted the most influence. They concluded that the implication is that communities attach more value to honesty, fairness, transparency, accountability and participation in decision making than to monetary donations alone. This supports Stakeholder Theory which argues that an organization is better performing when it has strong relationships with those impacted by its operations. It also indicates that those areas that have suffered environmental degradation and empty promises from oil companies may be more receptive to ethics and authentic involvement.

The strong influence of community engagement highlights the need to engage community residents in the design and implementation of the CSR programs. When individuals are given a chance to have a say in the decisions that impact their lives, they tend to be more supportive of corporate activities and more willing to work with organizations. Corporate philanthropy was positively and significantly related to community impact and organization performance ($\beta = .22, p = .002$). This shows that through the scheme of donation, scholarship, medical assistance and community project, company could enhance the community people's living standard and company acceptance. But the weaker impact than ethical practice and community engagement indicates that financial assistance alone cannot ensure enduring community trust.

The results reveal that the effect of environmental sustainability initiatives on community impact and organizational performance was not significantly moderated by political instability ($CESI \times PI, p = .081$). The upshot of all this is that political instability has neither positive nor negative influence on the effect of environmentally sustainable initiatives on community impact and organizational performance. The research also showed that corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability programs, ethical practices and community involvement, which are the four dimensions of CSR, significantly predicted community impact and financial performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. Of these dimensions, ethical practice ($\beta = .32, p < .001$) and community engagement ($\beta = .27, p < .001$) were the strongest predictors. This indicates that host communities value honesty, transparency, accountability, fairness, and participation more than they value other forms of financial support. The finding supports Stakeholder Theory, which argues that organizations are more likely to be successful in the long-term if they establish strong and positive relationships with their stakeholders (Freeman, 1984). It also indicates that communities who have been harmed by environmental damage and have been betrayed by oil companies are more likely to be swayed by ethical conduct and genuine participation in decision-making than by CSR initiatives that are primarily focused on financial aid.

These environmental projects involve technical and physical work, such as environmental clean-up, tree planting and shoreline stabilization work, which in some cases may be carried out during political turmoil. Consequently, they are less susceptible to political turmoil in the short term than other form of CSR actions. However, the result bordered on significance, and political instability was still found to have a direct negative effect on community impact and organizational performance ($\beta = -.21$). This demonstrates that environmental sustainability programs are not insulated from political instability. Over time, political interference, weak institutions and poor governance may attenuate the effectiveness of environmental CSR initiatives. This result is in line with Aye-Agele et al. (2025) who highlighted how environmental CSR interventions in the Niger Delta are mostly reactive, disjointed and subject to political disruption thereby compromising their capacity to engender long term impact.

The pronounced positive impact of community engagement reaffirms the necessity of engaging community members in CSR endeavors. Organizations enjoy more support and cooperation from communities when the communities have been part of the decision-making, project planning, and project execution. People also become more trusting and confident in an organization when they have the chance to have a say in things that concern them. This result is consistent with participatory development theory and the Social Exchange Theory, which underline trust, cooperation and mutual benefits as key elements that help to establish robust and sustainable firm-community relations. Likewise, corporate philanthropy had positive and statistically significant effect on community impact and firm performance ($\beta = .22, p = .002$). This means that funding, scholarships, health care programs and infrastructure initiatives will always be very important means of bettering the lives of community members and fostering acceptance of agencies. But the fact that it is less powerful than ethical behavior and community involvement points to the fact that philanthropy on its own cannot sustain the community's long term trust and support. Interventions of this nature may be perceived by communities as band-aids or as actions inspired by corporate self-interest, rather than authentic endeavors to promote sustainable growth.

The impact of environmental sustainability initiatives on community impact and organizational performance was positive and significant ($\beta = .17, p = .047$), but this effect was much weaker in strength than those of the other two dimensions of CSR. This result demonstrates that environmental responsibility is still relevant value in the Niger Delta region where the people have suffered decades of oil spills, gas flaring and environmental degradation. The implication is that activities of conservation and environmental protection can enhance community welfare and lead to organizational success. This is consistent with the consensus based on the Triple Bottom Line framework that believed organizations would be able to sustain success if they pursue economic goals while fulfilling social and environmental responsibilities. Yet the modest effect might reflect this: there are those in the community who continue to question the efficacy of environmental remediation and/or mitigation projects, particularly in communities in which prior environmental interventions have been perceived as too little, too late, and reactive rather than prophylactic.

The results also indicated that political instability was significantly negatively related to community engagement and organizational performance ($\beta = -.21, p < .001$). This implies that the likes of insecurity, bad governance, leadership wrangles, corruption, and fragile institutions undermine the efficacy of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, and impede community uplift. Further findings revealed a significant moderation effect of political instability on the relationship between corporate philanthropy, ethical practices, community engagement and organizational/community outcomes. Negative interactions indicate that the positive effects of these CSR activities diminish with growing political instability. The moderation effect was the strongest for community engagement ($\beta = -.16, p = 0.001$) suggesting that unstable political environment hampers an organization's efforts to build trust, foster community participation and sustain collaboration between the organization and host community. Such hurdles could undermine the success of CSR efforts and diminish the potential for achieving sustained positive effects over time.

Nonetheless, political instability was not a significant moderator between the environmental sustainability activity and community impact or organizational performance ($\beta = -.09, p = .081$). This suggests that environmental sustainability programs are somewhat insulated from short-term political barriers because they are often technical and involve physical and environmental clean-up, remediation, environment restoration work, which can be performed in the midst of transitory

political disruption. The findings suggesting that the results might be different in a situation of long-term political instability that may impede environmental CSR programs through destruction, poor environmental policies, bad governance, and erratic implementation. Overall, the study infers that CSR activities are positively related to community impact and organizational performance in Rivers State, but political stability, strong institutions, community trust and good relations between corporation and host community when exist, have an impact. In areas of pronounced political instability, the beneficial impacts of CSR initiatives may be reduced, thereby hindering firms from achieving their social and development goals.

The results reported need to be interpreted with consideration of several limitations. The data were gathered through self-administered questionnaires and as such, some respondents might not have given the ground truth. Additionally, the study adopted a cross-sectional research design with data collected at a single point in time, which inhibited the determination of temporality in the associations between CSR endeavours and organizational and community-related outcomes. Subsequent studies are encouraged to employ longitudinal designs, to involve objective indicators of conflict and development, and to collect data from multiple sources in order to enhance the validity and reliability of findings. Also, a comparative research between Niger Delta states and resource producing regions in other countries will assist in ascertaining the generalizability of the findings.

5.1 Conclusions

The result of this study indicates that corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities in Rivers State have the potential to positively impact community and organizations, if not constrained by the prevailing political instability in the state. Findings revealed that all the CSR constructs under study (corporate philanthropy, environmental sustainability practices, ethical practices, community engagement) were positively associated with community quality of life and organizational performance. Yet ethical practices and community engagement had the strongest effect. This means organizations that are transparent, accountable, reliable and engage the community participating in the work they do and the decisions they embark on, have a higher chance of success with their CSR initiatives in particular to regions plagued by conflict and political upheaval.

The findings also revealed that the performance of the organization and the development of the community are adversely affected by political instability. It diminishes the good results brought on by many corporate social responsibility (CSR) measures. The findings revealed that political instability had a strong influence on the community impact and organizational outcomes of corporate philanthropy, ethical practices, and community engagement. This implies that in Rivers State, it is difficult for an organization to pursue long term development objectives through CSR under the conducive political environment. Nevertheless, environment sustainability actions sustained positive impact even in the era of political turmoil. These findings suggest that environmental programmes might be more resilient to short-term political disruptions than are CSR which are so heavily reliant on social interaction and community engagement.

The study concludes that the effectiveness of CSR activities in rivers state is largely influenced by the political climate of the environment. CSR activities are more effective in a peaceful and stable environment with good governance. As such, CSR approaches adopted in stable regions would not be as successful in the Niger Delta if they failed to take account of local realities such as political instability, conflict and community needs.

5.2 Recommendations

On the basis of this study results, the implication for practice is that firms in Rivers State and other politically unstable regions should craft CSR initiatives that are cognizance of local political issues. Bodies should formulate adaptable policies and risk mitigation strategies, as well as community-based monitoring systems, to support the sustainment of impact of CSR initiatives in the face of political strain, insecurity or social upheaval.

Companies ought to be transparent and collaborate with the ordinary people of the communities in which they operate. The research found that when companies are honest, live up to their promises and listen to the concerns of the people who live in their communities, it is ultimately a win-win for both the corporation and the community. Companies need to consult with members of the community when deciding what it is going to do that has impacts on them. This will increase the trust, make the relationship between company and community better, and the CSR programme more effective in the long run.

The research also suggests that it is necessary for government agencies to strengthen the supervision over the fulfillment of CSR by enterprises, particularly commitments on environment protection. There must be adequate monitoring and regular public reports so people can know what companies are really up to. This will contribute to increased accountability of companies, diminished grievances from communities, increased public trust, and improved relations between companies and communities' local communities in Rivers State.

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